

Research on Psychological Consultancy Activities for Students of the Present Teacher In Secondary Schools in Daknong Province, Vietnam

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ABSTRACT

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School counseling is a psychological support activity for students when they have behavioral and emotional problems, difficulties in learning or future career orientation. School counseling is not yet widely practiced in Vietnam, and there are frequently insufficient experts to carry out this function, as in industrialized Western countries. The majority of homeroom and topic instructors will serve as their own school counselors. There are numerous unsatisfying issues while approaching minors due to a lack of experience and understanding of child psychology. The purpose of this article is to recount the actual circumstances surrounding psychological counseling sessions that homeroom instructors conducted with students in junior high schools in Dak Nong Province, Vietnam. Research topics and techniques: utilizing a descriptive cross-sectional research of 456 industrial teachers from 8 junior high schools in Dak Nong. According to the study's findings, the majority of educators believe that instructors in Dak Nong are now engaging in effective and extremely successful school counseling (77.8%). The best and most useful guidance for kids on academic issues comes from teachers, as well as gender and reproductive health issues; friendship; love; family relationships; emotions and behavior. Teachers employ direct counseling (face-to-face) the most and most successfully in terms of its application in psychological counseling for students. The way that homeroom teachers interact with their pupils varies. Homeroom teachers are quite successful and frequently work with parents to provide counseling. We use the findings of this study to create a counseling skills training program for homeroom instructors in Dak Nong province, Vietnam.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The early 20th century saw the birth of psychological counseling, which is now experiencing rapid global growth. It offers clients efficient psychological assistance, helps them maintain psychological equilibrium, and improves coping skills. with challenges in life and social interactions, in the direction of a better life (Tran Thi Minh Duc, 2012).Psychological counseling programs at schools in Vietnam have recently drawn increased attention.

The Ministry of Education and Training published Document No. 9971/BGD&DT-HSSV on: Deployment of Counseling Work for Students in 2005 to direct and advise divisions, institutions of higher learning, and other organizations involved in the execution of the school counseling program (Ministry of Education and Training,

Number: 9971/BGD&DT-HSSV v/v: Implement counseling work for students., 2005).

In 2011, the Ministry of Education and Training released the Charter of Secondary Schools, which stipulated that teachers in general, and classroom teachers in particular, have the responsibility of not only instructing and educating students, but also counseling and assisting them in resolving academic difficulties (Ministry of Education and Training, 2011).

The "Continuous training program for secondary school teachers" was created in 2011 by the Department of Teachers, the Ministry of Education and Training, and administrators of educational institutions (Ministry of Education and Training, 2011) (Ministry of Education and Training, 2011). There are no documents directing the methods, processes, or abilities of the homeroom teacher for activities, and there are no explicit rules

on how the homeroom teacher must provide psychological counseling to student.

In 2011, to implement psychological therapy for high school pupils, the Ministry of Education and Training has released Circular 31: High schools must comply with Ministry of Education and Training requirements as of February 2, 2018. There must be a student-focused psychological therapy organization in the media (Ministry of Education and Training, 2011). (Hoa, Linh, & Tran Van Thuc, 2007)

Secondary school kids are the focus of special attention since they are going through a unique stage of psychological, physical, and social development, which causes a number of psycho-social issues. rich and intricate. Students require guidance on how to view and approach life positively. Without the company, pupils would get disoriented and struggle to overcome their own obstacles in life and at their future jobs. Numerous studies on school mental health conducted in recent years indicate that over 20 % of school-age children suffer from psychological disorders, and approximately 19.5 % of students in primary and secondary schools experience issues about mental health (Do Van Doat, 2018); (Do Ngoc Khanh, 2008)

Students require psychological assistance, learning-related therapy, family, friend, and teacher counseling, as well as counseling on interests, gender, and personal development (Le Minh Nguyet, 2018)... However, because the majority of the teachers are relatively new, school psychology counseling is having issues. Since teachers have not received training in the fundamental concepts and abilities of counseling, working with pupils to solve difficulties is primarily dependent on experience. (Nguyen Thi Hang-Phuong, 2009)

In order to improve the capacity of psychological counseling for homeroom teachers of secondary schools in this area, we researched the actual situation of performing school psychology counseling in the province and proposed a training program. We realized the need to train a team of homeroom teachers with knowledge and skills in psychological counseling for Dak Nong province. *The above research results are the results of the project "Research and propose solutions to foster psychological counseling skills for homeroom teachers of junior high schools in Dak Nong province"*

2. RESEARCH APPROACHES

The study employed a synchronized combination of numerous techniques. The trustworthiness of the research findings will rise with the addition of methodologies.

2.1. Questionnaire-based survey method: to examine how secondary school head teachers rate their own psychological counseling abilities; the benefits and challenges they face while providing psychological counseling to students; and the training they feel is necessary to advance in this area.

2.2. Gather information regarding psychological counseling abilities in secondary school head teachers through interviews with instructors, according to the discussion and interview method. In order to assure impartiality and reliability within the allowable error, the mathematical statistical approach is employed in this area to process, analyze, and quantitatively and qualitatively evaluate the research findings. The program is called SPSS/Conquest.

3. RESEARCH RESULTS

3.1. The actual situation of organizing psychological counseling activities at secondary schools in Dak Nong province

3.1.1. Current state of psychological counseling programs for kids at schools in terms of efficacy

Table 1: According to the homeroom teacher, the junior high school's psychological counseling programs are effective.

Efficiency level	N	%
Inefficient	6	1.4
Less effective	95	20.8
Effective	312	68.4
Very effective	43	9.4
Total	456	100.0

According to Table 1's findings, 77.8% of teachers believe that psychological counseling programs now offered to children at schools are successful or extremely effective. Additionally, it received a less effective and ineffective rating from 22.2 percent of the teachers.

Table 2. Level of participation in psychological counseling activities for students of homeroom teachers at junior high schools

Participation level	N	%
Never	0	0
Rarely	36	7.9
Sometime	163	35.7
Frequent	257	56.4
Total	456	100.0

The survey results reveal that the majority of homeroom instructors at the school participate occasionally and frequently in psychological therapy for kids (35.7%and 56.4%). However, there are still a few homeroom teachers that don't often do it (7.9%).

3.1.2. The current state of psychological counseling provided to pupils by homeroom instructors at the school, including its format.

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Table 3, which summarizes teachers' views on the content and format of psychological counseling offered to students nowadays in schools, demonstrates how varied, rich,

and highly successful the counseling content and formats used by instructors are. the following

Table 3. Content and form of psychological counseling for students of the homeroom teacher at the secondary school

Content		Performance level		Efficiency level	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD
1	Sex and reproductive health	3.20	0.730	2.89	0.584
2	Vocational guidance	3.38	0.701	2.94	0.599
3	Friendship	3.41	0.708	2.91	0.617
4	Love	3.09	0.750	2.83	0.664
5	Relationship with family	3.36	0.697	2.94	0.587
6	Study	3.73	0.564	3.04	0.607
7	Emotions and behavior	3.27	0.715	2.89	0.616
Form					
1	Direct (face-to-face exchange)	3.61	0.568	2.94	0.613
2	Indirect (via phone, email, chat, etc.)	3.14	0.710	2.81	0.634
3	Coordinate forms	3.22	0.737	2.77	0.651

Teachers referenced the learning-related content the most and the most effectively when it came to psychological counseling for students (Mean = 3.73 and 3.04), followed by friendship. Family relationships (Mean = 3.36 and 2.94), professional

advice (Mean = 3.38 and 2.94), and (Mean = 3.41 and 2.91). - When it comes to psychological counseling for students, face-to-face counseling is the approach that teachers employ most frequently and most successfully (Mean=3.61 and 2.94).

3.1.3. The current situation of homeroom teachers' approach to students

Table 4. Teachers' opinions on how to approach students of the homeroom teacher

Student approach	Performance level		Efficiency level	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Students find their own way to the counseling room/psychological consultant	2.51	0.864	2.56	0.759
Counseling teachers actively approach to help students	3.65	0.537	3.05	0.597
Homeroom/subject teachers bring students to the counseling room/counseling teacher	2.81	0.891	2.57	0.729
Discover and arouse students' needs through other activities such as extracurricular activities, through seminars, etc.	3.44	0.636	2.96	0.647

According to the instructor's assessment of the homeroom teacher's present method of instruction, the homeroom teacher employs a variety of methods. Detecting and stimulating students' needs through activities, such as activities outside of class time, through seminars, etc., is executed to the greatest extent (Mean = 3.65), followed by "The counselor actively approaches to aid students." The highest effect is "Students discover themselves in the counseling room/psychological consultant" (Mean =3.44), followed by "The homeroom/subject instructor takes students to the counseling room/counseling teacher" (Mean =2.81).

The homeroom teacher's assessment of the effectiveness of the current approach to students reveals that "The counselor actively approaches to help students" (Mean=3.05), followed by "Discovering and arousing the needs of students through other activities such as extracurricular activities, through seminars, etc.," is the most effective strategy. (Mean=2.96).

3.1.4. The truth about homeroom instructors' participation in activities involving psychological counseling for secondary school pupils

According to the teacher's evaluation of how well the homeroom teacher coordinates psychological counseling

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sessions for middle school students at the school, "professional teachers have coordination with subject teachers and other teachers" is implemented at the highest level (Mean=3.73), followed by "teachers in collaboration with parents"

(Mean=3.72), and the lowest level is "teachers in collaboration with experts in different areas" other professional establishments" (Mean=3.73).

Table 5. Homeroom instructors' participation in student psychological counseling activities

Coordination work	Performance level		Efficiency level	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
The homeroom teacher cooperates with the subject teachers and other teachers	3.73	0.532	3.13	0.717
The homeroom teacher cooperates with the parents of the students	3.72	0.540	3.16	0.678
The homeroom teacher cooperates with the school administration	3.65	0.550	3.09	0.689
Homeroom teachers collaborate with experts from other professional institutions	2.46	1.013	2.48	0.820

The homeroom teacher has coordinated with the parents of the students, which is the highest effective level (Mean = 3.16), is followed by "Head teacher with coordination with subject teachers and other teachers," which is the second-highest effective level (Mean = 3.13), and the lowest effective level is "Homeroom teacher" collaboration with experts from other professional institute.

This finding also demonstrates that homeroom instructors undertake more coordination work in psychological counseling activities for secondary school students, which results in a higher level of effectiveness. In contrast, the coordination work for secondary school students is more successful. If the homeroom instructor only applied it sparingly, the effectiveness is also lower.

3.1.5. Conditions for performing psychological counseling activities for students

Table 6. Conditions for performing psychological counseling activities for students at secondary school

Condition		Performance level		Efficiency level	
Space		Mean	SD	Mean	SD
1	School counseling room	2.35	1.048	2.38	0.908
2	Boardroom	3.09	0.831	2.80	0.639
3	Classroom	3.43	0.738	2.86	0.667
4	School yard	2.77	0.855	2.62	0.764
5	Another function room in the school	2.32	0.958	2.54	0.871
Time					
1	Recess	3.12	0.886	2.70	0.708
2	Class	2.82	0.960	2.73	0.681
3	Outside learning time	3.26	0.767	2.79	0.655

Teachers' evaluations of the conditions for conducting psychological counseling activities for students at school today show that it is not fixed in one space and time, but quite diverse and flexible, taking place in many places. different spaces and at different times. Specifically:

- In terms of space, psychological counseling activities for students at the school are currently carried out most often in the classroom (M=3.43) and the Council room (M=3.09), and at least in the counseling room. school (M=2.35).

Evaluation of the effectiveness of using counseling spaces shows that it is most effective in the classroom

(M=2.86), followed by the council room (M=2.80), and The lowest efficiency was in the school counseling room (M=2.38).

- In terms of time, psychological counseling for students at school is currently done most outside of school hours (M=3.26), followed by recess (3.12).

Evaluation of the effectiveness when using time to conduct psychological counseling activities for students shows that the time outside of school hours is the most effective (M=2.79), followed by recess time (M=2.79). M=2.70).

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This result shows that the counseling activities carried out in the school psychology counseling rooms in schools are not effective.

CONCLUSION

The research results presented through the above tables have shown that secondary school students in Dak Nong want to be supported and advised by their homeroom teachers the most, especially on issues related to learning difficulties and problems. career guidance, followed by the need for counseling on friendships, and relationships with families. Research results show that the majority of teachers think that the current school counseling activities of teachers in Dak Nong are effective and very effective. Regarding the form and effectiveness of psychological counseling for students, the form of direct (face-to-face) counseling is used the most and most effectively by teachers. The content related to learning is consulted the most and most effectively by teachers, followed by career guidance and friendship. Homeroom teachers approach students in many different ways, in which, counselors actively approach to help students” is implemented to the greatest extent. Homeroom teachers mainly cooperate with parents in counseling and are also highly effective.

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